

Input to Curriculum Innovation of Physical Education in one Academic Institution

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Abstract - *This study aimed to assess the Physical Education (PE) in one academic institution in the Philippines as inputs to curriculum Innovation in terms of the university's vision, mission, goals and objectives, curriculum, faculty and Instruction and facilities; and based on the result, to propose plan of action for continuous improvement. The researchers used questionnaire adapted from the National Association for Sports and Physical Education set standards titled "Physical Education Teacher Evaluation Tool" (2007). Thirty-seven respondents participated in the study of the Physical Education of the institution. The respondents were the 8 deans, 20 department chairs and 9 Physical Education faculty members. The findings showed that all respondents agreed that the physical Education offered in the University strongly adheres to the university vision, mission, goals and objectives, curriculum, faculty and instructions, and facilities. The researchers proposed a plan of action for continuous improvement of Physical Education.*

Keywords: *Assessment, Physical Education, Implementation*

INTRODUCTION

Physical Education (PE) is both a discipline and a profession. As a curricular discipline, it promotes an understanding of the centrality of movement in daily life, in all its forms--from meeting functional requirements, providing opportunities for social interaction, analyzing the influence of contexts to one's well-being, to acknowledging physical activity and sports participation as significant cultural and health practices (Cariaga, 2014).

The 21st century marked the beginning of the second century for the profession of physical education. It is now high time for physical education to move on from its status as a "second class" profession to "first class" status. Substantial scientific evidence supports the role of physical activity in disease prevention and healthy lifestyle promotion, and quality physical education represents our best opportunity to provide all children with physical activity experiences that promote physical activity now and for a lifetime. The school setting provides a structured atmosphere in which to incorporate physical health activities and ideally develop healthy habits for life. Studies indicate that promotion of a healthy lifestyle taught in physical education classes can influence long-term health benefits such as reduced rates of obesity, heart disease, high cholesterol, diabetes, and high blood pressure (Cariaga, 2014).

PE, more than any other subject in the curriculum, is much more direct. It is a subject that is directly applicable and relevant to a learner's life in school, after-school and beyond schooling. Many of the numerous innovations in physical education have the potential to enhance the status of physical education and physical educators. For example, curriculum models such as experiential education and sport education have reshaped content, learning outcomes, and assessment in physical education. In addition, these models are redefining how teachers approach planning, instruction, and assessment. Even considering these innovations, physical education has had little success in enhancing its status in schools and communities. To improve the status of physical education, physical educators must first continue to promote and implement the curricular and instructional innovations that exist. Second, physical educators should explore ways to develop more community-based support for their programs.

Curriculum holds an outstanding place when seeking to promote innovation in education, as it reflects the vision for education by indicating knowledge, skills and values to be taught to students. It may express not only what should be taught to students, but also how the students should be taught. Curriculum innovations can include new subjects, combinations of old subjects or cross-cutting learning objectives. They may also take a form of new content,

concepts, sequencing, time allocation or pedagogy. Education systems need to become more innovative in their quest to improve quality, access and equity in a cost-effective manner.

Curriculum innovations can take a form of completely new subjects or combine old subjects with new ones. They can include, for example, new content, concepts, sequencing and time allocation within or across already existing subjects, while curriculum innovations can even translate to new and improved ways of teaching students. As well as introducing new curriculum within the existing school system, change initiatives can also take a form of establishing completely new kinds of schools with a certain kind of new curriculum.

The researchers, being MAPEH major in this situation, would like to assess Physical Education in Lyceum of the Philippines University as inputs to curriculum innovation. The process of conducting the investigation, as well as the results will make them more prepared in their chosen career in the future.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study aimed to assess the Physical Education (PE) in Lyceum of the Philippines University - Batangas as inputs to Curriculum Innovation.

Specifically, the study aimed to determine the status of Physical Education of LPU-Batangas in terms of its vision, mission, goals and objectives, curriculum, faculty and Instruction and facilities; and based on the result, to propose plan of action for continuous improvement.

METHODS

Research Design

The descriptive-evaluative method of research was used by the researchers to find out the existing condition of the Physical Education program of Lyceum of the Philippines University - Batangas. The design was used to appraise carefully the worthiness of the current study. In educational research, the most common descriptive methodology is the survey, as when researchers summarize the characteristics of individuals or groups or physical environments. The survey questionnaire was used, and an informal interview supplemented the description of the variables being studied.

Participants

The respondents were all the deans, department chairs, and P.E. faculty of Lyceum of the Philippines University with the total number of 37, by the time the study was conducted.

Instrument

The researchers used questionnaire adapted from the National Association for Sports and Physical Education set standards titled "Physical Education Teacher Evaluation tool".

The questionnaire is composed of four parts: Part I is about the vision, mission, goals and objectives; Part II refers to the curriculum; Part III is about faculty and instruction; and Part IV deals with the facilities.

Procedures

After brainstorming with group mates, visiting libraries, consulting knowledgeable people, and net surfing, the researchers came up with the topic and the needed frame of reference for the study. They then looked for appropriate instrument which was validated and distributed to target population. The researchers personally delivered the copies of questionnaire to each department and explained the details to guide the respondents in answering the items/indicators in the instruments. After enough time, the researchers personally retrieved the copies of the questionnaire through the same channel as they were distributed.

Data Analysis

All data gathered were tallied, encoded, and interpreted using descriptive and inferential statistics. Frequency count and weighted mean and were used to analyze the data obtained. The data was treated using 0.05 statistical software, PASW version 18.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1 presents the status of Physical Education in terms of vision, mission, goals and objectives (VMGO). The composite mean of 3.78 indicates that the respondents strongly agree that PE has a good VMGO. This implies that LPU is composed of students, faculty and support staff management who play important roles in the attainment of the university's VMGO.

It can be gleaned from Table 1. that very clearly, the school has a written mission and vision statement, goals and objectives evidenced by weighted mean of 4.00 ranked first and interpreted as strongly agreed means that the respondents completely agreed as this

is what they have expected for their students to learn through standard that is expected in the school's mission, vision, goals and objective.

Table 1. Status of Physical Education on LPU's Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives

Indicators	Weighted	Verbal	Rank
	Mean	Interpretation	
1. Syllabi and curriculum guide are aligned with current local, state, and national standards.	4.00	Strongly Agree	1
2. The mission and vision statement are shared and understood by learners and school members.	3.92	Strongly Agree	2
3. School board is involved in conducting needs assessments to develop the action plan.	3.83	Strongly Agree	3.5
4. School improvement plan is developed and communicated to all stakeholders.	3.72	Strongly Agree	5
5. Teachers and school board explain the school goals to parents and learners.	3.64	Strongly Agree	7.5
6. The plan is in place for regular supportive supervision.	3.69	Strongly Agree	6
7. The school has a clear line of communication system developed.	3.83	Strongly Agree	3.5
Composite Mean	3.78	Strongly Agree	

Legend: 3.50 –4.00 = Strongly Agree; 2.50 –3.49 = Agree; 1.50 –2.49 = Disagree; 1.00 –1.49 = Strongly Disagree

The result of the study is also supported by the fact that the school is proving several activities for the acknowledgment of the mission and vision of the school like the Mission Statement Awareness Week (MSAW) wherein the students participate for the recitation of the mission and vision of the school is also being held. For the goals and objectives to be successfully communicated to the students, each department provided every student with a student manual where the goals and objectives of the school is written. Aside from the student manual, the goals and objectives were also written on the syllabi and manuals used by the students.

The P.E. students and BEED/BSED have acquired needed teaching competence through relevant trainings and seminars. They internalized values and ethics expected of professors and teachers and become

responsible and productive members of society. Through the mission, vision, goals and objectives over play education students have an ability to facilitate learning of diverse types of learners and learning styles. They develop self-confidence through active participation and learn the strategies and techniques in accordance with relationships to support group effectiveness by being open, flexible, cooperative and respectful of others and being a team player. Physical education is a process of holistic development which consist of theoretical knowledge and is more than a subject that focus purely on practical skills. The students who usually liked physical education classes had positive attitudes toward physical education; besides that, they believed that PE teachers are considered good role models for students. Although items such as the plan is in place for regular supportive supervision (3.69) and teachers and school board explain the school goals to parents and learners got the lowest mean value, still, the respondents strongly agree that these activities are being practiced. Maybe at this time the respondents didn't notice the importance of explaining the goals of the university to the parents and students but then the institution must do this because this are the primary

Although items such as the plan is in place for regular supportive supervision (3.69) and teachers and school board explain the school goals to parents and learners got the lowest mean value, still, the respondents strongly agree that these activities are being practiced. Maybe at this time the respondents didn't notice the importance of explaining the goals of the university to the parents and students but then the institution must do this because this are the primary information that the parents and learners must know before they choose/select the school they preferred of. The goals that unriversity have may enlighten the parents and students to have a specific goal and some motivation to reach it.

Table 2 presents the status of physical education on curriculum having a composite mean of 3.67.

The respondents strongly agree on all the indicators that all the indicators showed the effectiveness of the implementation of the PE curriculum in LPU-B.

Different programs in LPU-B require specific descriptions of PE course like PE 1 which is Basic. Swimming and PE 2 which is Advance Swimming for Marine Transportation and Engineering students.

The 48-hour course must at least 85% make students comply with 4 feet up to 14 feet deep

swimming goal to be able to survive their safety of life at sea. And, for Criminology students they have PE 1 for Fundamentals of Martial Arts, PE 2 for disarming techniques as their practice for self-defense and will make them more prepared in their chosen career in the future.

Table 2. Status of Physical Education on Curriculum

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Syllabi and curriculum guide are aligned with current local, state, and national standards.	3.81	Strongly Agree	1
2. Instructional area is safe, orderly, and supports learning activities.	3.67	Strongly Agree	4.5
3. Adequate and developmentally appropriate equipment is accessible and utilized.	3.64	Strongly Agree	7
4. Instructional support materials are utilized to enhance the lesson.	3.69	Strongly Agree	3
5. Students understand and adhere to class rules, routines and behavioral expectations.	3.58	Strongly Agree	9.5
6. There is a behavior management plan that is fair, firm, and equitable.	3.58	Strongly Agree	9.5
7. Students are engaged in relevant, meaningful physical activity a minimum of 60 % of the instructional time.	3.67	Strongly Agree	4.5
8. Accurate records are maintained.	3.64	Strongly Agree	7
9. Progress toward school improvement goals is documented.	3.78	Strongly Agree	2
10. Student's performances are actively monitored and closely supervised.	3.64	Strongly Agree	7
Composite Mean	3.67	Strongly Agree	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.49 = Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 = Disagree; 1.00 – 1.49 = Strongly Disagree

And PE 3 for First Aid and Water Survival this is for rescuing preparation and saving life. Last is PE 4 or the Marksmanship and Combat Shooting as their preparation by practicing on how to use handguns for defensive combat. Enable them to practice shooting positions, quick draw and proper firing of handguns.

The effectiveness focuses on the extent to which the objectives of a program are achieved or are likely to be achieved. A program is seen to be effective when its outputs produce the desired outcomes. That there is an establish sustainability of the school curriculum that has a criterion that focuses of the program over the long term, the criterion is concerned with the maintenance, financial and economic viability of keeping the programmed going despite some challenges. The lessons plans and curriculum are aligned with current local, state, and national standards got the highest rank. Herman and Webb (2007) claimed that for an educational system to work, specific and major elements of the system must be aligned. They stressed that three main alignments must be in place for the educational system to function: alignment of assessment with the curriculum standards, alignment of teaching and learning with the curriculum standards and alignment of assessment to the teaching and learning. Alignment thus provides a sense of how well teachers and students are doing in their teaching and learning respectively. Baker (2004) found low performing schools' conversion into a standard-based system, significantly increased student achievement through strong curriculum alignment and standards-based instruction. Research has shown that curriculum standards alone do not produce higher academic achievement; however, research consistently supports student learning through a process of assessment of what they are taught (Porter, 2002; Rothman, 2002). Alignment between assessment and curriculum standards is a prerequisite to the success of student educational outcomes and overall educational improvement (Herman & Webb, 2007).

This is followed by the item progress toward school improvement goals is documented. This implies that LPU conduct systematic evaluation to ensure that standards of quality are being met and it has been documented.

Meanwhile, though the item that students understand and adhere to class rules, routines and behavioral expectations and there is a behavior management plan that is fair, firm, and equitable got the lowest ranked, still the respondents strongly agree that these are being practiced. Nickerson and Spears, (2007), stated "Challenging behaviors at school are a concern to society as schools are expected to be safe places for children to be.

Table 3 shows the status of PE on faculty and instruction having a composite mean of 3.70 which implies that teachers and faculty see consistency and

organization in their classroom as important because they allow the central focus of classroom to be on teaching and learning (Bain & Jacobs, 1990).

Table 3. Status of Physical Education on Faculty and Instruction

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Instruction is based on local, state and/or national physical education standards.	3.83	Strongly Agree	1
2. Supports physical education program goals.	3.75	Strongly Agree	2
3. Instruction is differentiated for all learners.	3.61	Strongly Agree	9.5
4. Content is linked to and promotes the transfer of learning within physical education units and among other subject content areas.	3.72	Strongly Agree	4
5. Student performance is continually assessed to guide instruction.	3.72	Strongly Agree	4
6. Lesson presentation is changed in response to observation of student performance and/or information from formative assessment.	3.67	Strongly Agree	7.5
7. Lesson pace is appropriate.	3.72	Strongly Agree	4
8. Independent learning is promoted, encouraged, and reinforced through daily assessments.	3.69	Strongly Agree	6
9. Engages students in learning by enabling all learners to participate through multiple modalities.	3.67	Strongly Agree	7.5
10. Content and tasks are presented concisely and clearly, emphasizing key elements.	3.61	Strongly Agree	9.5
Composite Mean	3.70	Strongly Agree	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.49 = Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 = Disagree; 1.00 – 1.49 = Strongly Disagree

The effective teacher recognizes academic instruction as central to his or her role. This focus on instruction guides not only the teacher's own planning and classroom behavior, but also comes across clearly

to students and represents the major element in a robust learning environment. A teacher may say to students, “It is my job to see that you succeed “or, “I want you to be prepared for life beyond the schoolhouse door.” Although effective teachers believe that students must be challenged, they also realize that students need to experience success.

PE faculty in LPU Batangas in supervised by an able Department Chairs who oversee the preparation and implementation of instruction. They revise all the syllabi yearly, submit and administer four major examinations and follow assessment guides and policy, lectures and return demonstration are observed every meeting with the professor as the key person in the classroom or gymnasium activity.

Effective teachers give high priority to foundational academic goals related to benchmarks or standards (Cawelti, 2004) and give secondary attention to higher-order personal and social goals (Zahorik et al., 2003). Physical education teachers work as state certified educators who are responsible for instructing students in health, fitness, and sports within a structured, K-12 school environment. Whether they are instructing kindergartners or coaching high school-aged adolescents, the process involved in becoming a physical education teacher is similar.

The respondents strongly agreed that the instruction is based on local, state and/or national physical education standards got the first rank with a weighted mean score of 3.83.

The next in rank were also strongly agreed by indicators.’ supports Physical Education program goals which got a weighted mean score of 3.75. The respondents agreed that the Physical Education had provided a program that provides learners with opportunities to learn motor skills, develop physical fitness and gain understanding about physical activity. Be able to participate in physical activity in form of play, games, dance and PE, and health education has immediate and long-term health benefits. Most importantly, it can improve a child’s quality of life. School can provide opportunities for students to engage in vigorous physical activity and are thus better placed amongst societal institutes to motivate students to live active lifestyles (Jenkinson & Benson, 2010). It is followed the 3rd highest in the rank were also strongly agreed by indicators.’ Content is linked to and promotes the transfer of learning within physical education units and among other subject content areas; student performance is continually assessed to guide instruction; lesson pace is

appropriate. This implies that the teaching strategies and lesson of PE teachers in LPU goes exactly as planned, and both the teacher and students learn from each other. On the other hand, the lowest rank and strongly agreed by the indicators is that instruction is differentiated for all learners and content and task are presented concisely and clearly got a weighted mean score of 3.61. This implies that PE teachers reinforce their focus on instruction through allocation of time to the teaching and learning process, and through their expectations for student learning (Brophy & Good, 1986); Cawelti, 2004; Cotton, 2000); Covino & Iwanicki, 1996; Molnar, 1999). That PE teacher focused on responsive teaching that gives students a range of ways to access curriculum, instruction and assessment. That helps engages students to interact and participate in the classroom in a richer way. It assumes that all students are different in their learning styles, strengths, needs and abilities and that classroom activities should be adapted to meet this difference.

Table 4. below indicates the status of physical education on facilities which got composite mean of 2.86 and verbally interpreted as Agree. That the respondents agreed that the availability of facilities had analyzed that the students had some motivation for learning in PE due to appropriate facilities and equipment's needed in different learning area of Physical Education. The major advantage in success of physical education are standardized facilities and sophisticated equipment. That the qualified facilities are very important for well-equipped and good area for physical education activities.

Among the indicators cited, school infrastructures are safe and secure, ranked first with a weighted mean score of 3.50. This implies that the indicators strongly agreed that LPU had safe facilities for students in PE. Lucas (2011) mentioned that classroom climate is more a product of interaction between and among teacher and student. The next in rank was the school outdoor facilities that are available on campus including pool which got a weighted mean score of 3.42. This implies that respondents strongly agreed that LPU contain the needs of teacher and students in terms of facilities, equipment and instructional materials. Marine students and other courses from LPU main campus both have gymnasium for indoor activities.

This is also used for specific events like PISTAKASAN and training area of athletes. Some facilities include sound system, score board and

playing court such as basketball, volleyball, badminton, and table tennis. On the other hand, the equipment's available are net, stand, antenna, balls, tables for table tennis, rackets, shuttle cock and paddles that are used as instructional materials of PE teachers.

Table 4. Status of Physical Education on Facilities

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. School infrastructures are safe and secure.	3.50	Strongly Agree	1
2. Indoor facilities are available on campus for organization of regular Physical Education courses, sports team practices, intramurals, intercollegiate competition on recreational activities for staff, students and other eligible users.			
2.1 Aerobic center/ cardio machine	2.58	Agree	8
2.2 Weight room	3.03	Agree	5
2.3 Physical Education Office	3.39	Agree	3
2.4 Dance Studio	2.61	Agree	7
2.5 Locker room (men)	2.42	Disagree	10
2.6 Locker room (women)	2.47	Disagree	9
3. Outdoor facilities are available on campus for organization of regular Physical Education courses, sports team practices, intramurals, intercollegiate competition on recreational activities for staff, students and other eligible users.			
3.1 Climbing wall	1.86	Disagree	11
3.2 Gymnasium	3.31	Agree	4
3.3 Pool	3.42	Agree	2
3.4 Sound System	2.86	Agree	6
Composite Mean	2.86	Agree	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.49 = Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 = Disagree; 1.00 – 1.49 = Strongly Disagree

On the other hand, the two lowest in rank and were disagreed by the respondents were climbing wall.” (1. 86) and “locker room for men” (2. 42). According to

NASPE 2001 guidelines in designing Physical Education, school should provide separate indoor and outdoor storage space for equipment that will be used during the instructional day and if space is available for intramural or after-school physical activity programs or interscholastic programs. Another school is encouraged to develop specialized facilities for a wide variety of activities such as swimming, outdoor fitness courses, climbing walls, and paddle tennis. And schools may provide separate locker rooms for physical education students, intramural and interscholastic programs, and for community recreation programs.

Table 5. Summary Table on the Status of Physical Education

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives	3.78	Strongly Agree	1
2. Curriculum	3.67	Strongly Agree	3
3. Faculty and Instruction	3.70	Strongly Agree	2
4. Facilities	2.86	Agree	4
Composite Mean	3.50	Strongly Agree	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.49 = Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 = Disagree; 1.00 – 1.49 = Strongly Disagree

Table 5. above shows the summary table on the status of physical education having a composite mean of 3.50.

The respondents strongly agreed that Lyceum of the Philippines University has a good Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives with a weighted mean score of 3.78 and got the highest rank. The next two in ranked was also strongly agreed by the indicators including Faculty and Instruction.” (3.70) and Curriculum” (3.67).

The respondents agreed that LPU-B provided a Physical Education Program through quality, research-based instruction that will surely help students attain knowledge and skills to be physically active and healthy for life in the 21st century. That they know that all students will be physically activated and educated, having acquired motor skills to perform a variety of physical activities, physical fitness knowledge, and intrinsic motivation to pursue a healthy and active lifestyle.

However, it also showed that facilities got the lowest rank but still the respondents agreed that LPU provides quality facilities which got a weighted mean score of 2.86. That the respondents agreed that the

availability of facilities had analyzed that the students had some motivation for learning PE due to appropriate facilities and equipment’s needed in different learning area of Physical Education.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of this study, the following conclusions were drawn:

The respondents strongly agree on the mission, vision, goals and objectives of the physical Education offered in LPU and a plan of action proposed for continuous improvement of PE in LPU-B in proposed.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The proposed plan of action may be implemented for the continuous improvement of Physical Education in LPU- B.

Table 6. Proposed Plan of Action for Continuous Improvement of PE in LPU-B

Key results area	Strategies/Methods	Person/s Involved
1. Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives Teachers and school board explain the school goals to parents and students.	Incorporate development of PE semesterly consultation with parents and students.	Deans PFMO PE Department Chair Faculty Students
2. Curriculum Students understand and adhere to class rules, routines and behavioral expectations. There is a behavior management plan that is fair, firm and equitable.	Intensify classroom orientation during first class. Strict implementation of management plan.	Faculty Students Faculty Students
3. Faculty and Instruction Instruction is differentiated for all learners. Content and task are presented concisely and emphasizing key elements.	Prepare instructional materials for all types of diverse learners. Use appropriate methodologies and start in a topic.	Faculty PE Department Chair Faculty

4. Facilities	Request for PE
Provision of facilities for climbing wall.	provision of Department Chair
Additional locker rooms for men and women.	Climbing walls Dean PFMO

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